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How can ‘societally-targeted research funding’ shape research networks and practices?¹

Irene Ramos-Vielba^{*}, Carter W. Bloch^{*}, Duncan A. Thomas^{*}, Rikke E. Povlsen^{*}, Mette L. Falkenberg^{*} and Andreas K. Stage^{*}

^{*}*iravi@ps.au.dk; carter.bloch@ps.au.dk; dat@ps.au.dk; ripo@ps.au.dk; mefa@ps.au.dk; ak@ps.au.dk*
The Danish Centre for Studies in Research and Research Policy, Department of Political Science, Aarhus University, Bartholins Allé 7, Aarhus C, DK-8000 (Denmark)

Aim and background

Funding is viewed to have a central role in defining the scope, content and direction of public research (Whitley, Gläser and Engwall, 2010; Bloch and Sorensen, 2015; Aagaard, 2017; Young et al., 2017). However, in many cases, we lack sufficient understanding of how specific funding designs may influence research in practice. This is particularly the case for the role of funding in shaping research to enhance societal goals. The mechanisms behind the translation of research into societal value are complex, potentially involving a number of different forms of interaction between varied actors (D'Este et al., 2018; Lindgreen et al., 2021; Smit and Hessels, 2021). Furthermore, along with multiple influencing factors in research developments, it is difficult to view the potential shaping of any single funding instrument in isolation. In any given period, a researcher or research team will often be involved in more than one research grant, generating complex dynamics through the direct and indirect interplay between diverse forms of funding (Aagaard et al., 2021).

This paper seeks to gain a better understanding of how the societal targeting of funding may shape research. We apply a recently proposed exploratory approach to characterize societal targeting in researcher funding, based on four key societal targeting dimensions: *interdisciplinarity*, *transdisciplinarity*, *prioritized research problems* and *user-oriented outputs* (Ramos-Vielba, Thomas and Aagaard, 2022). All these targeting dimensions of funding can potentially shape both researchers' research networks and practices towards societal goals (Table 1). Regarding research networks, the framework differentiates between societal targeting of interdisciplinarity networks among different academic disciplines and the involvement of nonacademic stakeholders in society (transdisciplinarity), e.g. private companies or non-profit organizations being included into the knowledge co-production network of the funded researchers. Two additional dimensions concern research practice; pursuit of specified societally oriented research problems; and specification for research outputs to be in some way user-oriented (e.g. policy reports, policy briefings, outreach materials, open datasets, and commercialization related outputs like patents, marketable products or services).

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Table 1. Four key societal targeting dimensions in research funding instruments

	Societal targeting dimensions	Targeted aspects	Targeted knowledge contributions to society	Targeting markers	Expected research
I	<i>Interdisciplinarity</i>	Research process	Cognitive perspectives Epistemic complementarity	Research networks (e.g. composition, role, involvement)	Inherently collaborative
T	<i>Transdisciplinarity</i>		Non-academic / tacit knowledge Co-creation of knowledge		Inclusively participative
P	<i>Prioritized research problems</i>	Research output	Problem-solving / societal needs Sensitive & relevant knowledge	Research practices (e.g. priorities, approaches, methods)	Suitably applicable
O	<i>User-oriented outputs</i>		Practical & useful knowledge Benefit & value to society		Widely usable

Source: Ramos-Vielba, Thomas, Aagaard, 2022

Through a series of in-depth case studies, we use this framework to examine how societally-targeted funding may shape research across these four dimensions, at the same time taking into account the potential influence of research, networks and activities outside of the main research funding in focus. We do this by probing condition for these dimensions prior to the funding in question, on activities and processes during funded research, and on plans, outcomes and expectations after the grant period.

Data and methodological approach

The analysis is based on in all twelve cases covering two selected fields (Renewal Energy and Food Science) in three European countries –Denmark, Netherlands and Norway. The study design sought to collect data on a combination of diverse cases –that may illuminate variation– for exploratory/confirmatory objectives, and most similar cases in specified variables –that may be broadly representative of the population– for potential comparison/generalisation purposes (Seawright and Gerring, 2008).

All three countries are small, advanced economies that have similar university and funding systems, though still possess a degree of variation in the composition and practices of specific funding bodies. Both fields are characterized by a broad range of research, from fundamental science to applied research, and by longstanding traditions for engagement with practitioners.

The case studies are centred around 3-5 year funded research projects started in 2015-16 and from three key national public funders –Innovation Fund Denmark (IFD); Dutch Research Council (NWO); and Research Council of Norway (RCN). The cases were identified using a series of criteria regarding the characteristics of funding programmes, field, time period, characteristics of the principal investigator (PI) (e.g. sex, academic position, type of organisation).

Data collection involved extensive desk research and interviews with the PI in each case study. This allows us to gain perspective on the funded project, initial conditions and relations, the research process, engagement of different actors, and expected or actual outcomes. Semi-structured interviews covered the selected funding instrument; four societal

targeting dimensions (I, T, P, O); and the broader funding context. Interviews with PIs were conducted (in-person and online) in last semester of 2021, and thereafter recorded, transcribed and coded with N-Vivo.

Table 2 outlines the analytical scheme for the paper, which investigates conditions before, during and after across the four targeting dimensions.

Table 2. Analytical scheme on funding shaping of research

Before vs. after	12 cases (country, field, sex)		
Before funding ↑	Usual / unusual	Same / new networks & practices	
	Reason(s)		
Funding requirements	Compulsory / encouraged / not required		
After funding ↓	Roles & value (I, T)	Adjustments & flexibility (P)	Utilization & users (O)
	Perceived changes		

Expected results

Preliminary analysis of interviews with PIs points to a number of tentative or expected results. Most PIs viewed a natural need for interdisciplinarity in their societally targeted projects, in order to address their research problem. Partners chosen from other disciplines were seen as complementary and only in very few cases amounted to significant departure from previous practices. However, in most cases, the projects involved collaborations with new academic partners. Only in a small minority of cases did the PIs view that the projects significantly changed their valuation of the benefits of interdisciplinarity.

Patterns are somewhat similar for nonacademic partners. In most cases, nonacademic partners were seen as a necessity for the project's success. Around half of the projects included nonacademic partners that the PI had previously worked with, though most included at least some new nonacademic partners. In around a third of the cases, the project had an impact on PIs' valuation of industry partnerships.

Results for prioritization of research problems and user orientation follow each other to a large degree. In both cases, choices made were viewed mainly as something they had wanted to do before the funding call. I.e. the call for the societally targeted funding was seen as a good fit with their research interests and desire to focus on societal application of their research. A small minority felt that the project had changed their views in terms of these factors, yet it involved a learning process.

Conclusions and policy issues

The preliminary results suggest a number of insights that can contribute towards a more systematic and comparable understanding of funding shaping across contexts, and will be valuable for policymakers, research funders, research evaluators, and scholars.

Some PIs do not report remarkable changes in the way they considered their networks and practices after the studied funded project. Most PIs in the sample were previously active in both basic research and collaborative research with industry partners. They express an ambition to pursue societal goals with their research and actively seek to build relationships with nonacademic stakeholders. Without opportunities for societally targeted funding, the academic-industry collaborations would not have been possible according for most PIs.

However, the preliminary results and indicated changes in some cases reveal intertwined funding research which also contributes to a shaping and research learning process (e.g. trial/error problem-solving techniques, cumulative tacit knowledge). The changes include incorporating new academic and nonacademic partners into their research networks, or addressing a wide range of collaboration challenges. With respect to research practices, scientific researchers seem to accommodate participants' diverse interests while navigating funding requirements, research needs and societal goals.

We also expect the study to yield a number of policy implications, suggesting potential advances in design, provision, monitoring or evaluation of funding and research, informed by real-world funded research contexts and dynamics.

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